

STATE OF AFFAIRS AND CHALLENGES IN SOLVING SYSTEMIC CORRUPTION THROUGH INTEGRITY

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Abstract

The state institutions in the Republic of North Macedonia have developed a culture of dealing with anti-corruption as external policy, meaning they are all either establishing a unit for anti-corruption or developing sector-specific strategies for dealing with corruption. It proves that the best method for establishing institutional mechanisms for building institutions resilient to corruption is to introduce procedures with built-in mechanisms i.e., procedures that prevent corruption within themselves alongside the external policies. These procedures can diminish the potential corruption that institution can face, or the risk is minimized. The paper will examine two institutions with concrete examples of how to build in anti-corruption procedures, such as the State Audit Office and the State Commission for the Protection of Corruption. For both institutions, the aim is to explore what type of built-in mechanisms or internal procedures can prevent corruption and ensure integrity.

Keywords: *integrity, policy, corruption, resilience, North Macedonia*

1. INTRODUCTION

Establishing institutional mechanisms for building institutions resilient to corruption through internal procedures, rather than addressing this issue through external policies, is considered the best method for preventing corruption. It is expected that applying these procedures can help diminish potential corruption. The promotion of integrity fosters an environment of trust and accountability, and it is crucial to sustainable and inclusive economic development (OECD, 2019). Often, state institutions approach anti-corruption as an external policy, an external add-on, rather than an embedded practice. However, professional management globally is trying to ensure honesty and integrity of public decisions and to broaden the perspective on ethics to include issues of transparency, professional responsibility, democratic values, civil liberties, respect of human rights, and compliance with the rule of law (Jreisat, 2022). Following these tendencies, the institutions in North Macedonia are prone to create special units or sector-specific strategies, despite the fact that these are often fragmented approaches and most of the time at risk of becoming formalistic exercises. This formality results in limited effectiveness of the undertaken efforts. What is missing is a deeper integration of integrity into the everyday functioning of institutions that should not be an isolated policy, but rather the foundation of sustainable governance and public trust.

This paper will examine the efforts of the state institutions in the Republic of North Macedonia in establishing a culture of dealing with anti-corruption as internal policy

through establishing special units for anti-corruption, developing sector-specific strategies for dealing with corruption through the system of integrity. Despite the general findings applicable to the Macedonian institutional environment, the special focus will be on the two particular institutions that have major responsibility in fighting corruption, i.e. State Commission for Prevention of Corruption (SCPC) and the State Audit Office (AUO). Both SCPC and AUO were selected since they have a dual role in the policy of integrity and prevention of corruption. Primarily, these two institutions should have an integrity system and built-in anti-corruption policies in their own procedures, i.e. for themselves, in the exercise of their legal powers. On the other hand, they supervise other institutions, i.e. they have a mandate to check whether another institution has abused or otherwise failed to conduct its operations in accordance with the law. Therefore, these two institutions, within the framework of their work and specific legal powers, have the authority to assess the work of other institutions, i.e. to check and give a finding whether another institution has and respects the policies for integrity and anti-corruption. The paper will answer what kind of preventive mechanisms and strategies they internally enforce, and do they prove to be effective. Methodologically, this paper will be based on the secondary sources, such as laws, bylaws, integrity guidelines, official reports and analysis that are publicly available. The final results of the research are pointing that, despite the external safeguards, the most successful strategy is establishing own system of integrity and procedures that will potentially prevent corruption within the institution. However, this system needs to be accepted as its own institutional culture and done in a more substantial rather than a formalistic way.

2 EXTERNAL AND INTERNAL MECHANISMS FOR THE FIGHT AGAINST CORRUPTION IN NORTH MACEDONIA

Integrity is the foundation of good governance and the fight against corruption, and at the same time, it is a strategic and sustainable response to the risks of corruption. It proves to be one of the most effective and most accepted mechanisms in international practice for preventing corruption. In essence, integrity means a firm adherence to a moral code by an individual based on relevant ethical values and normative principles (Feldheim, 2022). Establishing an integrity system in institutions contributes to eliminating the possibilities for the emergence of various forms of corruption and unethical behaviour in the public sector. The main idea of the system of integrity is to reduce the corruption risk, understood as an internal or external weakness in state bodies, public enterprises, and other public sector institutions, expressed as a specific procedure that opens up the possibility of corruption. This includes conflict of interest, incompatibility of functions, receiving gifts and other illegal payments, lobbying, fraud, inappropriate use of discretionary powers, illegal financing of political parties and campaigns, lack of a whistleblower protection system, trading in information or its unauthorized use, as well as non-transparency of procedures, documents and other issues that are of importance for the integrity (Pro-TRACCO, 2021).

Within the Macedonian legal framework, integrity means legal, independent, impartial, ethical, responsible, and transparent performance of activities, with which individuals protect their own image and the reputation of the institution for which they are responsible. That means they prevent risks and suspicions of possible corruption, thus ensuring confidence in the integrity of the performance of public functions and in the work of public institutions (Law on Prevention of Corruption and Conflict of Interest, 2019). This is in line with the international standards and what is assumed to be the public

integrity, referring to consistent alignment and adherence to common ethical values, principles, and norms of support. That means prioritizing the public interest over the private one (OECD, 2017).

There is no specific definition of corruption, but in general, we can say that this is a direct or indirect gain, for oneself or for another, through abuse of public office, public authority, and/or official duty/position. In essence, it means that the one who performs a public function gives priority to their own private interest over the public one (Handbook for Integrity Officers, 2022). The notion of public interest is also difficult to define, but in a democratic society it is accepted that working for public interest means service towards the protection of the fundamental freedoms and rights of man and citizen, recognized by international law and established by the Constitution. This includes prevention of risks to health, defence and security, protection of the environment and nature, protection of property, freedom of the market and entrepreneurship, as well as enhancing the rule of law and prevention of crime and corruption (Pro-TRACCO, 2021). That can be in the same line but also as an opposite to the private interest, understood as material or immaterial interest of an official, which may influence his decision-making in the exercise of public powers and official duties. That can potentially lead the official in a conflict of interest, or a situation in which the private interest of an official may influence his impartiality in the exercise of public powers or official duties.

The concept of integrity encompasses all institutions at the local and central levels of government, including the system for combating corruption. Despite the absence of a clear definition of the main postulates related to the fight against the corruption, the legal frame in North Macedonia, through the Law on Prevention of Corruption and Conflict of Interest (2019); Criminal Code (1996 with changes and amendments); Law on Whistleblower Protection (2015); Law on Lobbying (2021); Law on Public Procurement (2021); Law on Public Financial Control (1990 with changes and amendments) in addition to the Law on Prevention of Money Laundering and Financing of Terrorism; Electoral Code; Law on Administrative Servants; Law on Public Sector Employees, etc., (n.b. some of them will be presented in the next section), penalize the behaviours that are at odds with or against established social values aimed at preventing and fighting the corruption.

2.1 Legal and institutional framework

In the efforts towards fighting corruption, the country has developed an extensive legal framework in which the Law on Prevention of Corruption and Conflict of Interests and the Criminal Code form the main pillar that have legal provisions on corruption-related offences. The Complementary laws — on whistleblowers, lobbying, public procurement, and financial control (Law on Whistleblower Protection; Law on Lobbying; Law on Public Procurement; Law on Public Financial Control) provide additional safeguards. At the strategic level, the National Anti-Corruption Strategy 2021–2025 sets institutional priorities. The undertaken international obligations stemming from the UN Convention against Corruption (2004) and Council of Europe conventions on corruption (1999), are reinforced by international commitments which demand not only compliance but also systemic change.

On the other hand, the institutional architecture is also broad. The main institution in the fight against corruption is the State Commission for Prevention of Corruption (SCPC), which leads those efforts, and it is supported by the State Audit Office and the Bureau for Public Procurement. The Ministry of Justice, the Ministry of Interior, and the Public Prosecutor's Office all have roles in anti-corruption policies enforcement.

Additional support comes from the Financial Police, Customs Administration, and other oversight bodies.

Importantly, as an internal procedure, all the institutions in the public sector designate Integrity Officers (*лица за интегритет*) who act as internal supporters for the integrity policies, linking daily operations with broader anti-corruption frameworks. Therefore, the laws and the institutions provide the external mechanism, which checks the efficiency of policies and procedures for implementing the integrity concept, but the integrity officers are part of the internal mechanism. The internal mechanism consists of the responsibilities of the management in the institution itself, then of the designated integrity officer and other employees in the institution who work on the implementation of the integrity system, and their joint duty is, above all, to establish the so-called institutional climate for integrity. This is improved and perfected through special integrity training, development of methodologies, and guidelines for implementation (Guidelines for the Implementation of the Integrity Policy for State Bodies and Public Sector Institutions, 2021).

3 THE SYSTEM OF INTEGRITY AND ITS ELEMENTS

The integrity system rests on several key aspects and envisages the key elements. To start with, effective prevention and management of conflicts of interest is one of the most direct gateways to corruption. Preventing and managing conflicts of interest ensures that private benefits do not compromise public duties. The ethical codes and professional standards set expectations for behaviour. Ethical codes should translate abstract principles into daily guidance. The transparent and merit-based human resource management serves to reduce nepotism and clientelism and merit-based human resources policies are critical in a context where nepotism and political favouritism are persistent risks. The system also emphasizes rational and efficient use of public resources, since misuse of resources is one of the most common forms of corruption. Rational management of public finances and assets is crucial to reducing corruption risks in procurement, budgeting, and everyday operations. Transparency and access to information are treated as legal obligations, not optional values. Transparency and access to information allow civil society and citizens to monitor institutions. Discretionary powers are controlled by embedding rules into procedures, reducing opportunities for abuse. On the other hand, the protection of whistleblowers ensures that individuals who expose wrongdoing are safeguarded, thereby strengthening institutional accountability, i.e. it creates an institutional culture against corruption. Finally, quality management ensures institutions not only prevent corruption but also improve continuously, and it provides reliability (Handbook for integrity officers, 2022).

These elements are targeting both individual behaviour and decision-making as well as the institutional structures and processes. The integrity embedded in procedures will build institutional resilience, i.e., by embedding integrity into procedures rather than treating it as an external check, institutions become more structurally resistant to corruption. In this system, the integrity officers, who are designated staff to ensure compliance and cultural change, play a vital role. They are the bridge between formal frameworks and practical implementation, promoting an integrity culture inside each institution.

Table 1: System of Integrity of N. Macedonia

Elements	Description / Purpose
Conflict of interest prevention and management	Early detection and proper management of conflicts of interest as a safeguard mechanism.
Enforcement of ethical codes and professional standards	Institutionalizes values of professionalism, impartiality, and integrity across institutions
Transparent and merit-based HR management	Reduces nepotism, clientelism, and politicization by ensuring fair recruitment and promotion processes.
Public resource management	Promotes efficient, transparent, and rational use of public resources.
Transparency and access to information	Enhances accountability and enables citizen oversight
Discretionary powers	Limits arbitrariness by introducing clear rules, procedures, and oversight mechanisms.
Protection of whistleblowers and reporting channels	Ensures legal guarantees, confidentiality, and safety for individuals reporting wrongdoing.
Quality management systems	Supports consistency, monitoring, and continuous improvement to reduce corruption risks

*Source: SCPC, *Integrity policy, n.d.*

3.1 The Integrity Officer

The integrity officer is appointed by the institution's manager and also has a deputy. The obligation to have a designated official for integrity is part of the integrity policy, and it is in line with GRECO recommendations (GRECO, 2025). This is applicable to all public sector institutions. Additionally, it is necessary to establish integrity working groups (teams) in institutions, wherever the number of employees in the institution and the distribution of work and tasks allow it, i.e., it is necessary to be done based on the size of the institution and the scope of work, with the task to support him/her.

The integrity officer is the communication link between the institution that appointed him/her and the SCPC. His/her function requires appropriate professional competencies and moral characteristics, communication and negotiation skills, ability to resolve conflicts, initiative, interest, and motivation for his/her function. The integrity officer should have organizational skills, tact, dedication, but also discretion and professional ethics. In other words, the person should have the skills necessary for the development and implementation of a specific anti-corruption practice, but also the ability to make adaptive changes required by a particular situation.

The integrity officer has broad tasks including: monitoring compliance with anti-corruption regulations; raising awareness and educating about anti-corruption; providing information on anti-corruption procedures and processes; cooperating with the SCPC, etc. (Handbook for integrity officers, 2022).

3.2 The Policy of Integrity

The adoption of an integrity policy is the first step towards institutionally establishing an integrity system, based on which the institutional commitment is first clearly highlighted, and then the integrity system is strategically introduced, implemented, and improved, which, in this way, both managers and employees are obliged to consistently implement. The integrity policy, as an official institutional document, is

signed by the appointed integrity officer, is published on the official website and on the institution's notice board, and can also be sent to all employees via e-mail (SCPC, Integrity policy, n.d.).

According to the Guidelines for Assessing the Risk of Institutional Corruption in the Republic of Macedonia (Guidelines) (2020), each public sector entity should prepare a risk analysis, i.e. systematically, at least once a year, to analyze the risks associated with the activities, develop appropriate plans to limit the possible negative consequences of these risks and designate employees who will be responsible for implementing the adopted plans. For that purpose, the Guidelines elaborate six steps intended for assessing the risk of institutional corruption. These steps aim to assist in the self-assessment of the institution. Additionally, each institution is obliged to establish an effective system of internal control and audit in accordance with the principles of public internal financial control. Managing corruption risks is an important part of the system. Management structures are responsible for assessing and eliminating risks that contribute to the occurrence of corruption, embezzlement, fraud, conflict of interest, use of influence and connections for the purpose of obtaining preferential treatment or any other form of illegal or unethical behaviour (Guidelines, 2020).

For all identified corruption risks, the institution should determine indicators (sub-risks), i.e., take into account the indicators from the Guidelines taking into account: 1) The probability of the identified risk occurring (probability refers to the frequency of the risk occurring); 2. The impact of the risk, i.e., the effects or consequences that arise if the risk occurs (effects refer to the consequences caused by the occurrence of an event). In this way, it is determined whether the risk has a low, medium, or high level of impact and probability (Guidelines, 2020).

3.3 Monitoring and evaluation of the system of integrity

The process of monitoring the implementation of the integrity system involves assessing the level of implementation of the elements of the integrity system in the institution, and should be implemented at two levels. First, at the level of the institution, and then at the level of the competent institution, the SCPC. The integrity system consists of several interdependent elements, which have different legal backgrounds, and therefore institutions have obligations to monitor and report on several grounds. These obligations are not an administrative burden but an opportunity to monitor the achievements of the institution and to obtain knowledge for the promotion of integrity (Handbook for integrity officers, 2022).

Institutional monitoring should determine the effectiveness of the policies and procedures implemented to ensure consistent application of integrity elements, and measure the results of the measures implemented to reduce corruption risks. The process for implementing, monitoring, and reporting on the application of the integrity system is coordinated by the integrity officer. The SCPC monitors the implementation of the integrity system through a software solution and provides access to a questionnaire for all institutions. In this regard, the institutions are obliged to cooperate with the SCPC and to enable it to monitor the implementation of the integrity system (Handbook for integrity officers, 2022). In this way, relevant information is obtained for assessment and analyses of the situation, and based on it, the SCPC provides recommendations, guidelines, and indications for the successful implementation of the integrity system.

3.4 Some weaknesses of the system

It is generally accepted that a system of integrity has many benefits not only in building institutional resilience against corruption, but as well as in strengthening public trust and democratic governance. However, to be effective, the model should be sustainable, and its elements should become a daily practice that safeguards institutions. Considering this, the institutions must internalize anti-corruption mechanisms.

So far, when it comes to its implementation, it proves that anti-corruption policies often risk being too formalistic, and most of the necessary steps are only provisionally done. For instance, according to the latest ranking on the Corruption Perception Index (CPI) by Transparency International, North Macedonia has dropped 88 places, where the global average of the Index is 43, and in the EU 64 (Transparency International, 2024). On the other hand, it is a very complex matter, and it is not always easy to determine whether a certain behaviour in the public sector is corrupt or not. For that reason, it is necessary to assess whether there was an intention to misuse public resources for private purposes or whether there was disrespect for the law, ignorance of the principles of good governance, and the elements of integrity. However, whether someone will engage in a corrupt act or not depends on the integrity of the individual and on how effective the institutional mechanisms for preventing corruption are, i.e., to what extent the elements of integrity are implemented. For example, conflict of interest in itself is not corruption, but it is a risk of corruption. Effective management of conflict of interest implies that every state body and public sector institution should implement mechanisms for identifying conflicts of interest. It is recommended to prepare *an internal act*, consisting of criteria for assessing the risk of conflict of interest by job. The integrity officer, in the specific state body and public sector institution, is key to achieving this goal and should be the main point of communication and consultation. In the interest of greater accountability and transparency, each institution should encourage officials to openly discuss issues related to conflicts of interest.

Therefore, it is not enough for the institution to simply commit to zero tolerance for corruption, but all officials should be well acquainted with the integrity policy, the legal framework, their obligations and duties, as well as the disciplinary, criminal, and other procedures that can be initiated, and the possible consequences. In sustainable integrity systems, the motive for adhering to the rules should not be based only on the fear of possible consequences, i.e., possible disciplinary or criminal proceedings. Understanding the consequences of corruption has an important preventive role. All officials in the institution should be able to foresee how certain corrupt behaviour directly affects the quality of life of all citizens (Dobel, 2022).

Another important aspect is capacity building that should take place through regular education of employees for the appropriate application of the elements on which the integrity system is based, through trainings, workshops, seminars, as well as by providing advice on all dilemmas that may arise for officials in their daily work. It is recommended that these trainings be planned in the annual professional development plan.

4 THE SYSTEM OF INTEGRITY WITHIN THE STATE AUDIT OFFICE AND THE STATE COMMISSION FOR THE PREVENTION OF CORRUPTION OF NORTH MACEDONIA

4.1 Institutional resilience and its meaning

Resilience refers to the organization's capacity to anticipate, withstand, and recover from integrity risks while preserving its core values and public trust (Hollnagel, 2017; Bourgon, 2011). In theory, there are several identified categories of risk factors that shape audit institutions' vulnerability to corruption and unethical behaviour. It is assumed that those factors can be **contextual, organizational, individual, and working process factors** that interact with each other and influence institutional resilience. **Contextual factors** are considered to be the ones that are beyond the control of the organization, such as unclear or inconsistent legislation, the absence of a robust legal framework for preventing corruption, weak enforcement of conflict-of-interest and whistleblower protection laws, and non-transparent public finance processes. **Organizational factors**, in contrast, are the ones that fall within the institution's control and derive from its internal policies, management practices, and institutional culture. These could include integrity safeguards, specialized knowledge or practical auditing skills, adequate supervision, and internal communication. Pressures in the work environment, a perception of unfair treatment, or inconsistent enforcement of ethical rules may further undermine morale and increase susceptibility to misconduct (INTOSAI, 2020; Mungiu-Pippidi, 2015; OECD, 2022). At the **individual level**, resilience is shaped by the personal values, motivations, and competencies of engaged staff. Factors such as lack of knowledge, insufficient ethical awareness, inadequate practical training, or perceived unfairness in promotion can all contribute to unethical decision-making. Encouraging personal accountability through ethics training, transparent evaluation systems, and leadership by example can mitigate these risks and reinforce an integrity-driven culture (Kaptein, 2017). For building up resilience from internal factors and ensuring institutional integrity, there is a need to have policies against certain forms of misconduct. These include fraud, theft of resources, and conflicts of interest through the acceptance of gifts or engagement in outside employment. Resilience also depends on effective internal controls, transparent financial management, asset declarations, and regular ethics training aimed at strengthening the moral autonomy of auditors (UNODC, 2021). Finally, **working process factors** relate to procedural vulnerabilities. Excessive personal discretion, non-transparent decision-making, poorly organized work processes, and gaps in vertical or horizontal controls can create opportunities for abuse or error. They fall under the scope of non-financial integrity threats—such as the improper use of authority, manipulation of information, or indecent treatment of colleagues and citizens—and further expose cultural and procedural weaknesses within the organization. Taken all together, it is evident that institutional resilience thus requires ethical leadership, optimizing workflow design, ensuring traceable and transparent decision-making, strengthening procedural oversight mechanisms, procedural transparency, and secure whistleblower mechanisms that protect those who report misconduct (INTOSAI, 2020; Kaptein, 2017).

4.2 Institutional Resilience of the State Commission for the Prevention of Corruption and the State Audit Office of North Macedonia

State Commission for the Prevention of Corruption (SCPC) and State Audit Office (SAO) are a central pillar of the country's efforts to strengthen integrity and accountability in the public sector and therefore, they need to demonstrate strong internal institutional resilience against corruption. In this section, the focus will be on SCPC and SAO resilience towards corruption. This research has its limitations and needs to be taken into account since it only covers the analysis of the legal competences of the analysed institutions. It is only based on the findings gathered through publicly available reports. Those findings are compared with the international standards and practices of what is considered to be a cornerstone of the system of integrity in such type of institutions.

As the supreme audit institution, the SAO serves as both a watchdog of public spending and a model of ethical conduct. Its ability to maintain independence and credibility in an environment marked by complex political, administrative, and social pressures is a critical indicator of state integrity and institutional maturity (OECD, 2020; INTOSAI, 2019). A resilient SAO not only exposes irregularities but also embodies the standards of transparency, accountability, and professionalism that underpin democratic governance. If we consider the institutional resilience and factors that are affecting it, it is obvious that the inefficient law enforcement, overlapping institutional competences, and poor coordination among oversight bodies weaken the institution's internal capacity as well as the external environment in which the institution operates. Such systemic deficiencies constrain the SAO's capacity to function effectively and independently, highlighting the need for harmonized legislation, stronger judicial cooperation, and more transparent governance structures (OECD, 2022; UNODC, 2021). For stronger institutional resilience, there is a need to strengthen internal governance systems, to establish clear operational guidance, and to promote a culture of integrity and accountability through ongoing professional development (INTOSAI, 2020). Strengthening resilience against such risks requires the consistent application of merit-based recruitment and promotion, robust conflict-of-interest management, and an internal culture that prioritizes ethical behaviour over political or personal loyalty (Mungiu-Pippidi, 2015; OECD, 2022). Taken together, these contextual, organizational, individual, and procedural dynamics illustrate that institutional resilience from corruption cannot be achieved solely through external regulation or punitive measures. It depends on an integrated approach that combines legal clarity, ethical leadership, sound internal management, and a professional culture grounded in public service values. Within North Macedonia's broader trajectory toward European integration and public administration reform, the SAO's resilience is both a reflection of and a contributor to national integrity, and in this sense, it needs to be strengthened.

Alongside SAO, the SCPC of the Republic of North Macedonia represents a cornerstone of the country's integrity system and democratic accountability framework. As the key independent body responsible for preventing corruption, monitoring conflicts of interest, and promoting transparency in public life, the SCPC operates at the critical interface between political power, public administration, and civil society. Its resilience is vital for maintaining public confidence in the state's capacity to uphold the rule of law and safeguard ethical governance (OECD, 2020; UNODC, 2021). The resilience of this institution, as it is in the other example, is challenged by systemic weaknesses that extend beyond the SCPC's direct control. These are the same as the ones that are affecting the work of SAO, since they are working in the same political system and social environment with limited interinstitutional cooperation. To be able to maintain its preventive and

investigative functions, there is a need to harmonize legal provisions, alongside clear delineation of institutional responsibilities, and strong political commitment. At the organizational level, the SCPC faces internal challenges related to resources, management, and institutional culture. Pressures in the work environment, perceived political interference, or feelings of unfairness can create vulnerabilities to misconduct or discourage professional integrity. To counter these risks, the SCPC must cultivate a strong ethical culture supported by regular integrity training, transparent career advancement, and mechanisms that protect staff from retaliation or undue influence. Strengthening internal controls, digitalizing asset declaration and reporting systems, and ensuring traceable and evidence-based decisions are essential for reinforcing procedural integrity and organizational learning. Overall, the SCPC's institutional resilience depends on its capacity to adapt to external pressures while preserving its legal independence, operational transparency, and professional integrity. Within the context of North Macedonia's ongoing alignment with European standards of governance, the resilient SCPC is essential. Its endurance and credibility are fundamental to building societal trust in institutions and advancing the broader national agenda of transparency, accountability, and good governance.

CONCLUSION

The fight against systemic corruption in North Macedonia requires more than external safeguards and formalistic compliance—it demands a deeply embedded culture of integrity within public institutions. This paper has shown that while legal and institutional frameworks provide a necessary foundation, true resilience against corruption stems from internal mechanisms that prioritize ethical conduct, transparency, and accountability. Elements such as the management of the conflict of interest, ethical codes, transparent HR practices, and whistleblower protection are not merely procedural requirements but strategic tools for institutional transformation. The role of integrity officers emerges as pivotal in bridging policy and practice, fostering a climate of trust, and ensuring that integrity becomes a lived institutional value.

The theory suggests that integrity systems—when implemented substantively—can significantly reduce corruption risks. Within the Macedonian context, both SAO and SCPC are key institutions in supporting the system of integrity. Therefore, the system of integrity needs to be embodied in their work as well as their internal procedures. The research reveals the persistent challenges in this respect. Fragmented implementation, lack of capacity, and a tendency toward formalism undermine the effectiveness of integrity policies. For integrity systems to succeed, they must be internalized by all officials, supported by continuous education, and reinforced through meaningful monitoring and evaluation. The goal is not only to prevent corruption but to cultivate institutions that serve the public interest with professionalism and moral clarity. Ultimately, building institutional resilience through integrity is a long-term endeavour. It requires commitment, adaptation, and a shift from reactive anti-corruption measures to proactive ethical governance. Only then can North Macedonia move toward a more transparent, accountable, and democratic public sector.

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